

Council of cyborg elders

Before starting the experiment you need to explain the purpose and risks of the experiment to the cyborg elders, and only their approval will allow you to recruit the volunteers. What points do you think you need to address to convince the elders you have thought about all the ethical aspects of the experiment? (You discover in your pocket an old ethics application template, would you like to use it to prepare your speech?) Choose the points from the list:

1. Description of the experiment's methodology
2. Your scientific successes during the last 5 years
3. Resources needed to conduct the experiment
4. Your love for sci-fi and, in particular, for "Star Trek"
5. Sensitivity of data
6. Participants risks and possible negative consequences
7. Your active participation in the Open Science Community of the Netherlands
8. Participants remuneration
9. Your recollections of everything that went wrong last time you ran an experiment

Insert the numbers in the field below (e.g. 1, 2, 3...) to unlock the next step!

*Vereist

1. *

What are the necessary attributes of a trustworthy data

You are still facing the council of cyborg elders...

They want you to publish the dataset from the experiment as openly as possible, so that as many cyborgs across the universe can benefit from it. You need a trustworthy repository. Even though you have not used any repositories in this universe, you can identify a trustworthy one with the help of a list of necessary attributes, right?

1. Have a beautiful flashy website with pictures of attractive cyborgs
2. Convert all files to formats that can only be opened by proprietary software
3. Ensure long-term persistence and preservation of datasets (e.g. up to 4000 days after publication)
4. Be supported by a research community or research institution
5. Delete the contents of the repository every year to clear space
6. Provide deposited datasets with persistent identifiers
7. Mail a present for every submission to the corresponding author
8. Send emails about new items added to the repository

repository?

9. Allow access to data without unnecessary restrictions
10. Provide clear terms of data use and data access (or license)
11. Facilitate anonymous reviewer access for embargoed data
12. Notify the Corporate Overlords about every submission with openly accessible data

Insert the numbers in the field below (e.g. 1, 2, 3...) to unlock the next step!

2. *

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